

BEST PRACTICE

This is part of a series of guidance documents produced by the NADIR FP7 project. There are various international and national standards in place for undertaking infectious work in animals with pathogens that require high containment facilities. These guidance documents be examples of how these can be practically interpreted

Best Practice for House Keeping in Animal High Containment Facilities

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Scope of this Best Practice

- 1.1.1 This Code of Practice describes an effective housekeeping and cleaning regimes for high containment animal facilities to ensure a safe and healthy work place for all staff and visitors.

GOOD HOUSEKEEPING AND SAFE PRACTICE

- 2.1 Good housekeeping is a prerequisite for a safe working environment and it requires those working in containment facilities to be proactive in contributing to the tidiness of their particular areas. Pre-work planning can help ensure that work areas are uncluttered. Effective arrangements must be implemented to ensure that the work environment is maintained throughout, to appropriate health, safety and hygiene standards.
- 2.2 High containment animal facilities are designed with barriers to only allow authorised and appropriately health cleared personnel entry. Therefore cleaning must be undertaken by either personnel using the containment facility or by specific personnel health cleared and trained for this task.
- 2.3 In order to facilitate cleaning of the personnel only areas of the facility, of a barriered unit must be tidy with no clutter or unnecessary items left on work surfaces and floors.
- 2.4 Changing Rooms should be maintained with adequate supplies of clean clothing (including socks and underwear where necessary), locker space, foot wear and personal protective equipment for the staff that will using the facility.

Where showering facilities are used, these should be maintained with adequate supplies of soap, shampoo and towels for the staff that will use the facility.

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SOPs and logbooks must be in place and include as a minimum:

- procedures and frequency for cleaning equipment such as Microbiological Safety Cabinet (MSCs), fridges, freezers and other equipment such as fire extinguishers;
- procedures and frequency of cleaning of changing rooms, showers corridors, store rooms work surfaces and floors; and
- cleaning procedures in the event of a spillage.
- Sealability testing and checking
- Building Defect notification and actions
- Alarm testing e.g. fire
- Personal Respiratory Protective Equipment (RPE)

2.5 The following cleaning rules apply to all types of work

It is the responsibility of the person who has used the MSC or any other equipment to ensure that it is disinfected before any other person uses it. Disinfection must be using the approved disinfectant and contact time relevant to the organism that is being studied

- The inner surfaces of the safety cabinet and any other working surface must be cleaned and disinfected after every working session.
- Where applicable the tray under the MSC working surface must be decontaminated periodically (e.g. once per month) as stated in the SOP.

All work surfaces must be cleaned with an approved and validated disinfectant (at the correct dilution for the correct contact time) at least once monthly. Floors must be cleaned with the disinfectant stated in the SOP weekly basis . Dry sweeping and dusting must be avoided.

- Unused equipment and materials must be properly stored or removed and not allowed to collect in the facility or block aisles and exits.
- It is best to minimise the amount of packaging and boxes, that enter in to the contained suite as they. must be decontaminated when they are removed ..
- Fridges and other equipment and must be cleaned regularly and they must be free of expired materials.
- Sharps bins must be disposed of safely and promptly and must not be filled past the fill line.
- As part of the housekeeping regime hand wash sinks (including the taps) must be regularly cleaned. Soap and paper towels must always be available. The liquid soap dispenser should not be topped up from other bulk stocks. Single use paper towels must be used for drying hands. Cloth towels must not be used.
- All waste must be properly disposed of in suitable containers and emptied regularly as stated in the SOP.
- Cleaning must be recorded in cleaning log books.

PEST CONTROL

- 3.1 High containment buildings should be designed to be rodent proof. However it is possible that rodents could be introduced in items such as bales of hay so rodent barriers and baits must be in place with baits being checked regularly.
- 3.2 High containment buildings should be designed to be proof against insect entry and escape. However it is possible that insects may be introduced into the building (by entering animals but also animal food, or litter) so insect traps must be in place and be checked and cleaned regularly to monitor any insects that are gaining access to the building.

DISINFECTANTS AND CHEMICALS

- 4.1 Containers of fresh disinfectant and dilutions equipment must be readily available in the animal facility. In such containers, a label containing the disinfectant name, dilution performed, person in charge of the preparation, date of preparation and expiration date should be mandatory.
- 4.2 Diluted disinfectants must be regularly changed as stated in the SOP to ensure efficacy.

MONITORING

5.1 Monitoring

To ensure the effectiveness of and compliance with this Best Practice the following arrangements should be in place.

5.1.1 Proactive Monitoring

Monitoring takes place proactively in the following ways:

- Formal audit by the Institute Health and Safety Department which includes topics related to all aspects of working in containment.

5.1.2 Reactive Monitoring

Monitoring takes place reactively by accident/incident reporting

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Document History

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